

D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES- WP3.5

Report on occurrence of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce in different regions in Europe

**Workpackage 3 of
JRP22-FBZ4.1-
TOXOSOURCES**

Responsible Partners:
ISS, BfR, SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.5
Project Acronym	JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES
Authors	Marco Lalle (ISS); Martha Betson (UoS), Gema Alvarez Garcia (UCM), Rafael Calero Bernal (UCM) and Pikka Jokelainen (SSI).
Other contributors	TOXOSOURCES consortium
Due month of the report	M59
Actual submission month	M59
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 30.11.2022
Dissemination level	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s): Coordinator of IMPACT project.....</p>

D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.5 REPORT ON OCCURRENCE OF *T. GONDII* IN SELECTED FRESH PRODUCE IN DIFFERENT REGIONS IN EUROPE

BACKGROUND

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/>);

Work Package:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3 Multicentre survey to fill the key existing gap: role of fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat salads);

Task:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3-T3 Multicentre pilot survey on *T. gondii* in fresh produce in Europe.

Project Leader: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI; Deputy Project Leader: Joke van der Giessen, RIVM.

WP Leader: Marco Lalle, ISS; Deputy WP Leader: Anne Mayer-Scholl, BfR.

Task Leader: Marco Lalle, ISS; Deputy Task Leaders: Nadja Bier and Anne Mayer-Scholl, BfR.

Contacts: Marco Lalle, marco.lalle@iss.it; Pikka Jokelainen, PIJO@ssi.dk

TOXOSOURCES addresses the research question – **What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *T. gondii* infection?** – by using several multidisciplinary approaches and novel and improved methods to yield robust estimates that can inform risk management and policy makers.

TOXOSOURCES WP3 aims to fill the knowledge gap concerning the relevance of fresh produce contamination by *T. gondii* oocysts as an infection source for humans. Objectives of TOXOSOURCES WP3:

- ✓ To identify and assess the most appropriate procedure to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce.
- ✓ To provide an overview of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce and the environment.

- ✓ To conduct a risk-based pilot study based on available prevalence data (literature review), data on food production chains, EU trade patterns of selected fresh produce and available consumption data (WP2).
- ✓ To evaluate *T. gondii* oocyst contamination in selected fresh produce commodities by a multicentre pilot survey in representative EU regions.

As part of the work done in TOXOSOURCES WP3, a multicentre study was designed and conducted over a twelve month period (October, 1st 2021 to September 31th 2022) to evaluate *T. gondii* oocyst contamination in pre-packed ready-to-eat (RTE) mixed salad, collected in ten European countries, by detecting *T. gondii* genomic DNA according to the SOP developed and implemented among consortium partners (Deliverables D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 and D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.3).

At the time of writing this Deliverable, sample collection was completed (UCM; PIWET; UoS; SSI; NVI; VRI; ANSES; BfR; INIAV; ISS) and analyses of samples (DNA extraction and qPCR) were still in progress. This deliverable summarizes key aspects of the work done, while detailed description of methods and results of the multicenter study will be reported in a scientific publication (Lalle et al., in preparation).

PURPOSE

The purpose of the multicentre study was to perform the most extensive analysis so far conducted in representative European countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Norway, Spain, United Kingdom) to assess the occurrence and prevalence of contamination by *T. gondii* oocysts in pre-packed RTE salads. RTE salads represent a specific category of fresh produce characterized by a noticeable increase in per-capita consumption in Europe over the past few years. RTE salads are minimally processed (e.g. removal of salad head core, if present, and external leaves not suitable for processing, washing, drying and packaging) and they are intended to be consumed without additional treatment; with a microbiological risk being associated with their consumption. Indeed the number of reported cases of bacterial gastroenteritis being associated with RTE salads consumption is increasing in recent years. However, the risk of acquiring foodborne parasitic infections and diseases, particularly toxoplasmosis, associated with consumption of RTE salads has been underinvestigated. TOXOSOURCES is a large, unique research consortium that was able to address this knowledge gap with this multicenter study.

DESIGN OF SAMPLING STRATEGY

To design a risk based sampling strategy for the study, we used multiple approaches as the data are scattered and not easily available. Information on *T. gondii* oocyst prevalence in fresh produce and trade/consumption of RTE salads in European countries were collected and combined. Data concerning *T. gondii* oocyst prevalence in fresh produce were retrieved from the literature review (including the grey literature) conducted as part of TOXOSOURCES WP3-T2 (Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4; López Ureña et al., 2022).

To define the most representative RTE salad(s) sold and consumed in Europe, in July 2020 a questionnaire on RTE trading and production was prepared and administered online (using the Jisc Online surveys platform available through the University of Surrey: <https://surrey.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/toxosources-rte-product-trade-and-distribution-chain>) to a list of Food Industries, from small to big enterprises, and to Food Industries Trade Association operating in Europe, that were contacted individually by email (Annex 1 and 2). A request for exchange of information was forwarded to EFSA Focal Points to obtain data at national level on annual production, imports, exports and consumption of RTE salad products (Annex 3). Finally a survey was conducted in spring 2021 by TOXOSOURCES partners at local supermarkets to determine what RTE salad products were available and their composition. Based on estimated prevalence of *T. gondii* oocyst contamination, the sample size was calculated using EpiTools and R v4.0.4.

KEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Representative RTE salad(s) sold and consumed in Europe

Questionnaire on ready-to-eat (RTE) product trade and distribution chain in the EEA

An email with the link to the questionnaire (<https://surrey.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/toxosources-rte-product-trade-and-distribution-chain>) was provided to 31 potential participants, including Food Industries, from small to big enterprise, and Food Industries Trade Association operating in Europe (Annex 1 and 2). The survey was accessible from 9th July 2020 to 28th February 2021. Seven enterprises (5 from Italy, 1 from Belgium and 1 from France) completed the questionnaire.

Since a data confidentiality and protection policy was adopted for this survey, allowing the use of the data only for research purposes within the TOXOSOURCES project, the full dataset cannot be made publicly available and therefore only the main findings of the survey are reported below. The low response rate, biased towards a single country, prevented efficient use of these information gathered for the definition of the risk based sample strategy. Two out of the seven enterprises indicated possible interest to provide samples to be tested.

It is noticeable that among the responders, parasites were generally not listed as important foodborne pathogens that could be present in RTE salads, suggesting that the food industry did not perceive contamination of fourth range products with foodborne parasites as a risk for consumers. Indeed no specific measures or analyses were listed to detect any foodborne parasite, also because no specific legislation is in force at European level. It is important to note that in the RTE salad production chain, products from a single country (European or non-European) can be widely distributed across Europe. As shown for other pathogens, under these circumstances, any contamination event occurring along the production chain at a single or multiple production site(s) might affect consumers in different European country at the same time.

Request for exchange of information to EFSA Focal Points

This approach provided some additional information: ten countries provided an answer to the request for exchange of information submitted to EFSA (Austria, Croatia Czech Republic, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania,

Portugal, Slovak Republic, Spain, The Netherlands) (Annex 3). Although general data on vegetable consumption and/or trade at national level were provided, no specific information concerning RTE salads to be used to define the risk based sample strategy was provided, limiting the use of the data from this source.

Survey on RTE salad on sale in local supermarkets

In an attempt to define the most common RTE salad mixes that could be purchased by consumers in the European countries involved in the multicenter study, project partners visited local supermarkets and collected the following information: supermarket name; salad brand; salad name, type of cultivation [Organic (Y/N)], salad origin (by country); name of the producer; name of the packaging company; location of the packaging facility; salad composition; barcode. Data were collected in Brno (Czech Republic), Copenhagen (Denmark), Paris (France), Berlin (Germany), Rome (Italy), Pulawy (Poland), Lisbon (Portugal), Oslo (Norway), Madrid (Spain), and Guildford (United Kingdom). Only leafy green salad mixes were selected avoiding mixes with tubers (e.g. carrots) or other ingredients (e.g. seeds, herbs). In summary, survey involved 27 supermarkets, 34 brands, 165 RTE salad mixes (including 3 by organic cultivation). The composition of each salad was reported and listed to define the most common mixes available in the majority of countries. It was found that two types of salad mixes are the most common: baby leave and cut salad -mixes. The ingredients most commonly reported were:

- for baby leave -mixes: Spinach baby, arugula, baby lamb's lettuce; baby red and green lettuce
- for cut salad -mixes: Frisée (curly escarole); Radicchio (red); Endive; any green lettuce (e.g. Iceberg, roman, etc.).

Adopted sampling strategy

Sample type

Based on the literature review, the online questionnaire on RTE trading and production in Europe, and the survey of RTE salads on sale in supermarkets conducted by consortium members, it was decided that samples selected for the pilot study should be two types of salad mixes: baby leaves or cut salads -mixes, containing three to four ingredients including the following:

- **for baby leaves -mixes (BABY LEAVES):** Spinach baby, arugula, baby lamb's lettuce; baby red and green lettuce
- **for cut salads -mixes (CUT SALADS):** Frisée (curly escarole); Radicchio (red); Endive; any green lettuce (e.g. Iceberg, roman, etc.).

It was decided to purchase salad mixes from local supermarkets (selecting those widely present in each country) and, to enhance representativeness, that at least of two different brands for each type of salad mix should be selected, if feasible.

Timing of sampling

Due to seasonal variations in where salads might be grown and how salad is cultivated, it was decided that an equal number of salad samples should be collected in each season (autumn, winter, spring, summer) over the

period of one year. Where possible, sample collection should be done regularly throughout each season, with each laboratory performing sampling monthly (ideally, 7-8 samples each week).

Sample numbers

Based on the allocated budget and cost of analysis per sample, the collection of a maximum of 3200 RTE salad samples was planned. The breakdown of sample numbers per salad type and season is shown in the Figure 1. Sampling was planned to be carried out in ten countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Norway, Spain, United Kingdom) overall representing the north, south, east and west of Europe, with an equal number of samples (320 samples in total) collected in each country per season (approximately 40 baby leaves and 40 cut salad samples per country per season).

Figure 1. Summary of overall sampling in the proposed sampling strategy.

Power calculation

Based on limited published data and expert opinions, it was expected that between 1% and 20% of RTE salad samples will be positive for *T. gondii* oocysts with the molecular detection method. Considering a predicted prevalence of 1% and a confidence level of 95%, a sample size of 400 will allow the seasonal prevalence of oocyst contamination of RTE salad (baby leaves and cut salad) to be estimated to a precision of 1%, if the design effect is 1, and 2%, if the design effect is 4 (taking into account intra-cluster correlation at the country level). Considering a predicted prevalence of 20% and a confidence level of 95%, a sample size of 400 will allow seasonal prevalence of oocyst contamination of RTE salad to be estimated to a precision of 4%, if the design effect is 1, and 8%, if the design effect is 4 (taking into account intra-cluster correlation at the country level). A further consideration is the ability to detect differences in prevalence between different seasons. With a sample size of 400, the power to detect medium and large effect sizes is over 90%.

Table 4. Summary of precision of prevalence estimates and power to detect, small, medium and large effect sizes

Sample size	Design effect [%]	Precision of prevalence estimate (at 1%)*	Precision of prevalence estimate (at 20%)*	Power to detect		
				Small effect sizes [§]	Medium effect sizes	Large effect sizes
400	1	1.0%	4%	>80%	>99%	>99%
400	2	1.4%	6%	>50%	>99%	>99%
400	3	1.7%	7%	36%	>98%	>99%
400	4	2.0%	8%	29%	>90%	>99%

[%] Takes into account intra-cluster correlation at country level but cannot be estimated without data; * Considering a confidence level of 95%; [§] Significance level of 95%

Analysis strategy

Data analysis is in progress at the time of writing this deliverable and will be described in detail in scientific publication planned for 2023. Analysis will be carried out at a European level rather than a country level. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise the data. Associations between variables (e.g. season, salad type) and oocyst contamination will be explored using multivariable analysis, taking into account, if feasible, clustering at the country level.

Preliminary results

The sampling was successful and the SOP performed well in the study. A number of samples tested positive, and results of their further laboratory analyses are expected around the time of submitting this deliverable. The results indicate that *T. gondii* oocyst contamination is present in RTE salads sold in Europe.

Key strengths of the study include its multicenter design and sampling approach over one year, as well as using a standardized laboratory method for the detection. It should be emphasised that the molecular methods used cannot show the infectivity of the parasites, only the presence of their DNA. However, *T. gondii* oocysts are very resistant to environmental factors and the mild processing of RTE salads is not expected to inactivate them.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on data retrieved from different sources and by different approaches, a risk based multicenter study to investigate possible contamination of RTE salads with *T. gondii* oocysts was planned and successfully conducted in Europe. So far it is the first and largest survey conducted at the same time in different European countries to fill in the knowledge gap that is relevant to evaluate the risk for consumers to contract toxoplasmosis by consumption of RTE fresh produce. Preliminary results of this study indicate the occurrence of *T. gondii* oocyst contamination in RTE salads sold in Europe. This points out on the need to strengthen awareness and control along the production chain for RTE salads.

DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT

Preliminary results of this study have been presented at key international conferences (e.g. ICOPA 2022, APICOWPLEXA 2022). Scientific publication is planned for submission in 2023. Earlier steps of the work have been reported in Deliverables, presentations at conferences, and as scientific publications.

1. Gianluca Marucci, Nadja S. Bier, Alessia Possenti, Martha Betson, Rafael Calero-Bernal, Nadia María López Ureña, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Pikka Jokelainen, Marco Lalle. Molecular method for detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables: inter-laboratory SOP validation and multicentre field application. Oral presentation at ICOPA2022, Copenhagen, Denmark, Marco Lalle. Role of Fresh Produce. Symposium: TOXOSOURCES. Video on demand symposium at ICOPA2022, Copenhagen, Denmark.
2. Nadja S. Bier, Rebecca D. Berg, Rafael Calero-Bernal, Martha Betson, Umer Chaudhry, Filip Damek, Rebecca Davidson, Gema Alvarez-Garcia, Gro Johannessen6, Pikka Jokelainen, Nadia María López-Ureña3, Gianluca Marucci, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Weronika Piotrowska, Alessia Possenti, Jacek Sroka, Helga Waap, Barbora Zalewska, Marco Lalle. DEVELOPMENT, INTER-LABORATORY SOP EVALUATION AND APPLICATION OF A MOLECULAR METHOD FOR DETECTION OF TOXOPLASMA GONDII OOCYSTS IN READY-TO-EAT LEAFY-GREEN SALADS IN A MULTICENTRE STUDY IN EUROPE. Poster presentation at APICOWPLEXA 2022, Bern, Switzerland.
3. Marco Lalle. European multicenter survey of *Toxoplasma gondii* contamination in ready-to-eat salads. Oral presentation at the European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites 17th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites, Rome, Italy, 15-16 September 2022.

REFERENCES

- Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 SOP on detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce matrix <https://zenodo.org/record/4405243#.YHVhiOgzaUk>
- López Ureña NM, Chaudhry U, Calero Bernal R, Cano Alsua S, Messina D, Evangelista F, Betson M, Lalle M, Jokelainen P, Ortega Mora LM, Álvarez García G. Contamination of Soil, Water, Fresh Produce, and Bivalve Mollusks with *Toxoplasma gondii* Oocysts: A Systematic Review. *Microorganisms*. 2022 Feb 27;10(3):517. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms10030517.
- Slana et al. Molecular Methods for the Detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review. *Microorganisms* 2021, 9(1), 167; <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010167>; <https://zenodo.org/record/4647840#.YHVh7ugzaUk>